

A Brief Study on The Discussion of The Theme of Stockholm Syndrome in JaishreeMisra's "Love Story For My Sister".

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ABSTRACT

*This article is the study of the psychological response that people often associate with infamous kidnapping and hostage situations. The psychological response which occurs when hostages or abuse victims bond with their captors or abusers. Stockholm syndrome, a psychological behaviour or an adaptation to the habitat synchronizing with the best possible reality. This psychological connection develops over the course of the days, weeks, months or even years of captivity or abuse. In Lima syndrome, a captor or an abuser develops a positive bond with a victim; they may become empathetic to the individual's circumstances or condition. The theme of Stockholm syndrome is discussed by Misra in the novel by employing a three-perspective narrative structure, comprising of Margaret Wheeler, Tara Fernandez and Pia Fernandez. A few studies of recent times attempted to explain why 'Stockholm syndrome' may develop in victims, and several theories were put forward. In the context of the novel, young people like Margaret may be particularly susceptible to developing 'Stockholm syndrome' as they develop positive feelings toward the adults like Nizam whom they are dependent on for protection and provision of basic needs. By adopting a friendlier behaviour, the hostage may adapt better to stress captivity. Level of Stockholm syndrome that hostage experiences increases with better quality of treatment by the captor. The study will have a closer look with the novel "Love story for my sister" by JaisreeMisra. **Keywords:** Stockholm syndrome, captive, captor, sexual assault, hostage, captivity, defence mechanism, traumatic experience*

1.INTRODUCTION:

The status of Indian English Literature in the realm of world literature continues to reflect Indian culture, tradition, social values and Indian history. Indian Writing in English has won a lot of critical acclaim in the literary world and Indian authors have made it big with some fantastic masterpieces. Indian experiences of modern predicaments have been given expression by recent Indian fictional writers such as Amitav Ghosh, Kiran Desai, Vikram Seth, Rohinton Mistry, and JaishreeMisra. Among these famous writers, the majority of them have contributed to the genre, novel. One of the main themes of Indian English literature has been women and the way they are treated in the society.

2.WOMEN BEING A METAPHOR FOR VIOLENCE:

Over the past several decades, violence against women in fiction appears to have been normalised. It has, in the past two years, encouraged public conversations about sexual violence and power. It is important in this context to discuss the ways in which narratives of sexual assault and harassment of women and other marginalised groups are depicted in fiction. It is generally difficult to situate women in violent narratives because the writers have left no space for survivors to have voice. It is here that women writers have shown their bold resolve. When a woman transcends herself as a writer, she redefines the female individuality. She does this with the help of the potential she gains from the female aesthetics. This strikes a change in the mode of creativity – she transcends from

stereotypical creativity to direct creativity. She actively creates a sequence of her subjective experiences, which she wants to be heard by the public. JaishreeMisra is one such Indian author who took the literary world by storm with her debut novel '*Ancient Promises*', the story of a woman in search of her identity. She 'deplores duplicity' with her easy and engaging style of writing. Apart from writings on women, her interest lies in exploring history and spotting its relevance in contemporary life. The target of attraction of this project revolves around Misra's ability to bring in stories from two different dimensions, as seen in her work '*A Love Story for my Sister*'.

3. HISTORICAL IMPORTANCE OF "A LOVE STORY FOR MY SISTER":

Misra's *A Love Story for My Sister* would have been a historical fiction based on Margaret Wheeler and her abduction during the uprising of Cawnpore in 1857. The siege of Cawnpore was a key episode in the Indian Rebellion of 1857. The besieged company forces and civilians in Cawnpore were unprepared for an extended siege and surrendered to rebel force under Nana Sahib, in return for a safe passage to Allahabad. However, their evacuation from Cawnpore turned into a massacre, and most of the men were killed. As an East India Company rescue force from Allahabad approached Cawnpore, 120 British women and children captured by the sepoy forces were killed which later came to be known as Bibighar Massacre, their remains being thrown down to a nearby well in an attempt to hide evidence. Margaret Wheeler, daughter of General Wheeler was kidnapped during the uprising of 1857. Misra parallelly attempts to narrate this incident along with a story of contemporary relevance on Tara Fernandez, an 18 years old school girl, kidnapped and murdered in 1997. Strangely the two incidents are alike in its progression and are surprisingly separated by a period of 140 years. Both cases are clear evidences of Stockholm syndrome, a condition in which the hostages develop a psychological alliance with their captors during their captivity. Misra has employed a different storyline to capsule the life of Margaret as well as Tara, the former with a historical reference and, latter being a teenager, resident of contemporary Delhi.

4. A PERFECT BLEND OF HISTORY WITH FICTION;

JaishreeMisra mainly deals with Stockholm syndrome developing in both Margaret Wheeler as well as Tara Fernandez in her novel but unfortunately, the existing literature on the subject of Stockholm syndrome is sparse; the majority of the literature is based on case reports with little reference to how Stockholm syndrome was diagnosed, its significance or impacts on victims etc. Stockholm syndrome is rarely mentioned in peer-reviewed academic research. The major limitation for this study is reporting bias. Existing literature does very little to support its existence yet case studies demonstrate a possible pattern in the behaviour and experiences of people labelled with it. Despite of all these limitations JaishreeMisra has not only attempted to portray Stockholm syndrome but has also fictionalised it.

While Misra believes that fiction cannot completely solve the problems of the world. She does think that stories have the ability to shift perception. Writing historical fiction, as she had done in the past with '*Rani*', Misra points out that 'the membrane separating fiction and history was delightfully permeable'. But with a love story, there was a need to enter the preserve of fiction writer and to go into the most intimate space of private thoughts and conversations that even the best preserved history can only hint at. Poised as she is between these different worlds, Misra offers this book while bleakly asserting the unchanging brutality in human behaviour. It also allows for an opening in the conversation surrounding the crisis in masculinity in India today. According to Misra, it is this crisis that all need to address, if we are to make things safer for women.

JaishreeMisra's '*A Love Story for my Sister*' is remarkable in its way of blending simultaneously, two stories of historical as well as contemporary relevance. The novel brings out events from two different periods that are 140 years apart from each other. The story revolves around the lives of Margaret Wheeler, a historical figure from the 1857 uprisings and Tara Fernandez, a contemporary Delhi school girl. The essence of the novel relies in the way in which how two love stories unfold and how it engages the readers from different dimensions. Misra's invariant approach to this story is the highlighting element of the novel, as she introduces the concept of 'Stockholm Syndrome' in the

lives of these two young girls. The gradual happenings they encounter and the decisions they take, further moves the story to an unprecedented state. The continued trend of violence against women for no fault of their own becomes the author's focus of discussion throughout the novel.

As with most things, Stockholm syndrome is used by the writer to give a startling effect. The Syndrome is however, not a new concept, it is paradoxical in the way the captive feel sympathetic towards the captor. This led to Misra's broader interest in developing a love story with a different colouring that could effectively bring out the virtues of life and love with the glimpse of hope entwined with it.

The psychological response of Stockholm syndrome is developed within Margaret as she slowly discovers the sense of lenience within her captor. He is compassionate towards her, no longer being an insolent. It is a key factor that induces the development of the syndrome within Margaret. The captive, as part of her defense mechanism begins to sympathize with her captor. Nevertheless, it leads her to accept the situation. As a result, the defiance and aggression towards the captor is limited and thus, she begins to maintain survival in an otherwise potentially high risk scenario. This is evident in the book, as Margaret accepts the truth of being orphaned, having lost her parents and all her siblings. Nizam's confessions of the brutality that he has witnessed, is also an intuition of his natural reactions to evils against mankind.

A few studies of recent times attempted to explain why 'Stockholm syndrome' may develop in victims, and several theories were put forward. In the context of the novel, young people like Margaret may be Out there, it is madness... such things as no man should ever behold...women and children... they have... (*A Love Story for my Sister*, 103) particularly susceptible to developing 'Stockholm syndrome' as they develop positive feelings toward the adults like Nizam whom they are dependent on for protection and provision of basic needs. Several authors postulate that hope of escape may be an underlying cause. In the novel however, Margaret does not attempt for an escape, though she had quite a few chances. Margaret's personality was gradually developing the feelings and thoughts needed to survive the situation, her emotional and physical risk. It was an automatic, probably unconscious emotional response to the traumatic experience of being a victim. It might have affected the hostage and the hostage taker alike and has served to unite both, being victims of siege environment, against outsiders. This positive emotional bond between Margaret and her captor Nizam is a subject of defense mechanism. The Stockholm syndrome may save the life of Margaret and Nizam alike. This realisation has ultimately led her to be with her captor, anticipating a new life with him. To Margaret, it was easier to live far away from British compartments as she realises that even if she returns to her people, she would be treated nothing more than a social outcast. As for most cases, it is women uniquely vulnerable for being blamed for assault upon them. It psychologically traumatizes women and creates strong resentment among people of the region to which she belongs.

5. AN IDENTITY CRISIS IN THE VICTIMS:

Freedom always brings a sense of elation and relief. However, adjusting back to the real world after being held hostage can be just as difficult as abruptly learning it. Margaret knew that her fellow Britons would be pleased if she had returned but in her rescue laid lifelong imprisonment to the fate that had already befallen her and could never be erased. Margaret had no illusions. She was aware of how people talked and behaved in British cantonments and, after so many days in the captivity of a native sower, she would be considered soiled goods, to be pitied and reviled, a 'social pariah'. No one will willingly be her friend; no one would ever want to marry her. She would be condemned to a joyless spinsterhood. That, Margaret knew without a shadow of doubt, was the fate that awaited if Nizam, her captor and later her protector, took her to a British camp.

Margaret's decision to go with Nizam in one way, suggest her desire to survive. The psychological response of Margaret towards him also reveals her sense of trust and sympathy towards her captor. This is a significant part during a captive-captor relationship. She cannot help starting to feel less fear of him and less abhorrence. She no longer hates him and even asks him for a favour of finding her two brothers from the Madras presidency. Margaret also begins to wonder at her willingness to

allow so much faith in Nizam. She is now more willing to believe his earlier protestation as it was intended for her own safety. Nizam confesses his love for Margaret. It was not momentary, rather it was gradual. He vowed to remove her from the trouble and guard her with his life. By now, it was almost impossible for Margaret to distrust Nizam or his intentions. She expresses her consent of becoming Nizam's Muslim wife Mehrunnissa Begum, and leave for Peshawar. Though an English woman, and as she refuses to go back to her people, she converts herself to Islam. At certain level the loss of religious, traditional and language identity of Margaret could be considered as a direct consequence of the syndrome that has victimised her. However, she hoped for a better life in Peshawar duly with respect and honour, being Nizam's wife, and did not anticipate a comeback.

The theme of Stockholm syndrome is discussed by Misra in the novel by employing a three perspective narrative structure, comprising of Margaret Wheeler, Tara Fernandez and Pia Fernandez. All these three females contribute to present a unique narrative that is one way or the other, inter connected. The novel moves through Pia, who is a young aspiring novelist. She investigates the curious story of Margaret, who is one of the first known victims of Stockholm syndrome. Pia's interest in Margaret's story is in fact her quest to solve the mystery behind the missing of her own sister Tara Fernandez. There are apparent similarities between the two – both girls being eighteen years old during their abduction, both of mixed parentage and both being possible victims of Stockholm syndrome. The syndrome might have resulted in their disappearance along with their captor. The unusual bond that they formed with their captor, which forced them not to return, was the key factor that invited the attention of Pia. She assumes that her sister too might have fallen victim to such a syndrome that had affected Margaret one hundred and forty years ago. Thus while investigating across Margaret's life and attempting to compose a novel based on her, Pia is ultimately able to contrast Margaret and Tara's life. Misra's portrayal of binary narrative is suggestive of depicting the two stories of Stockholm syndrome in Margaret as well as in Tara.

6. CONCLUSION:

The summations of Stockholm syndrome often reveals certain features that the victims exhibit. In case of Tara, she experiences direct threats from one of her abductor, and was kept in isolation. However, throughout her escape with Himal, her second captor, she does not use her opportunity to escape. As they proceed their secret journey to Mukteshwar in the Kumaon Mountains, she fails to escape as she starts a strong sense of solicitude towards Himal. This eventually led her to identify that Himal was possibly in love with her. Though she felt tortured with the guilt of not contacting her parents, as the young teenage girl in her early twenties, Tara becomes relished, catapulted into such a grown up scenario. Her captor's attention towards her is identified as both flattering and endearing. This is contrary to what a woman might feel after her abduction and rape.

Most of the novels of Jaishree Misra lack concrete endings. They are open-ended. Even in *A Love Story for my Sister* Misra ends her novel abruptly and allows the plot to continue even after the end. The reason for this deliberate act on the part of the author may be she wants her readers to give vent to their own responses. The fictionalisation of Tara's love story is open-ended and it is up to the readers to ponder on possible ends according to their own perceptions. Misra uses the medium of literature as the poignant outlet to voice her feelings, thoughts and experiences concerning men and women. The novelist is not simply satisfied with the plot, storytelling or narration. She makes the readers become immediately conscious of her powerful assertion, which projects her female wrath against the dominant attitudes, denials and deprivations meted out to the victims by the victimisers. Apart from Jaishree Misra's *A Love Story for my Sister*, Lucy Christopher's *Stolen: A letter to my captor*, C.J Robert's *Captive in the Dark*, *Seduced in the Dark*, Kitty Thomas's *Comfort Food* etc are books which deals with Stockholm syndrome. Jaishree Misra is the first Indian author to employ Stockholm syndrome and attempt to update her readers with a new term along with her voice against the social evils like rape kidnaps etc. The novel '*A Love Story for my Sister*' was written as her response to the Nirbhaya gang rape incident (16th December 2012), now attained justice.